

TEACHER ATTITUDE TOWARDS MANAGEMENT OF CLASSROOM PRACTICES (A STUDY IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS, VISAKHAPATNAM CITY)

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Abstract

Teachers must be knowledgeable about a variety of factors that influence the classroom and the teaching-learning process, such as how the academic calendar works, how classroom arrangements are made, how students behave and how lessons are taught, as well as how evaluations are administered and how students perform in class. The primary role of a teacher in a classroom is to encourage students to develop good behavior and to help them learn. The main aim of this paper is to study the teacher attitude towards management of classroom practices. In this purpose the secondary schools in Visakhapatnam city have been taken as sample units and 360 teachers working in these schools are considered as sample respondent. These sample teachers are selected by stratified random sampling method where 180 male teachers and 180 female teachers have participated in this part of investigation. Thus, this research on management of classroom practices is based on modules and self-learning package on Behavior Strategies, if teachers provides guidance for effective classroom performance. It also contributes to the development of appropriate strategies for behaviour of teachers and also the students. When implemented systematically in real classroom setups, it can enhance students' learning and support positive classroom behaviour. Thus, teachers who have completed in-service teacher training using the modules and self-learning package can demonstrate a significant increase in their awareness and classroom practices of Behaviour Management Strategies, and consequently the on-task behaviour of students per class period. In this regard, the investigator would consider herself adequately compensated if the study's findings were used by teachers, educators, and policymakers to improve current classroom management practices and to conduct additional research in this pertinent but interesting and effective area.

Keywords: Teacher attitude, secondary schools, classroom practices, management.

Introduction

The present study was mainly intended to find out the effectiveness of in-service teacher training programme on management of classroom practices at the Secondary Schools. As the prelude to the experimental study, the extent of prevailing classroom management practices and the training needs of Secondary School teachers in the select five dimensions of in-service teacher training and management of classroom practices were identified with a view to preparing appropriate modules, self-learning package and in-service teacher training materials for the thrust area.

In this study, the In-service Teacher Training was identified by a multi-dimensional perspective of the teachers on Facilitating learner-centered innovative learning and work, Facilitating learner-centered innovative learning and work, and Facilitating innovative learning and work that is learner-centered. Assessing and monitoring learning processes and outcomes, developing and implementing programmes, schedules, training materials, and didactic methods, guiding and counseling learners, forming partnerships both within and outside one's own institution, and pursuing one's own professional development and creativity On the other hand, Management of early planning, physical arrangement, behaviour management, instructional management, and evaluation management are all included in the definition of Classroom Management Practices as a multidimensional construct. To answer the research questions posed and test the hypotheses formulated for the study, a preliminary analysis of the scores of the various variables was attempted. Following the study in retrospect, there is a brief description of the study's conclusions and a summary of the findings. On the basis of the study's findings, the chapter concludes with implications and practical suggestions.

The literature review

Brouwer and Tomic (2000)¹ suggested that when developing interventions to prevent and treat secondary school burnout, educators should consider students' perceived self-efficacy in managing classroom practices. Midthassel and Bru (2001)² asserted that a systematic effort aimed at improving teachers' classroom practices through a collaborative work environment that promotes reflection and learning had a beneficial effect on teachers' stress levels as a result of disruptive students, as well as their classroom practices. Weinstein et al. (2003)³ assert that the ultimate goal of classroom practices is to provide equitable learning opportunities for all students, not compliance or control. In order to implement culturally responsive practices in the classroom one must be able to recognise one's own ethnocentrism; be aware of students' backgrounds; be aware of the larger social, economic and political context; use culturally appropriate management strategies; and create caring classrooms. A discipline philosophy, prevention and procedure, positive integration, classroom rules, discipline procedures, negative consequences, positive consequences and parent communication were all part of Gregg's (2003)⁴ plan for effective classroom practices. To improve classroom management, Shechtman and Leichtentritt (2004)⁵ used affective teaching techniques in special education classrooms. Affective education is concerned with the personal lives of children, which includes their perceptions, emotions, and behaviour. An emerging education literature model of FEAR, proposed by Niles in his article 'Building classroom practices plan for inclusive environments from fear to FEAR',⁶ highlights four components of proactive inclusive practices that can replace the fear of diverse classrooms. In this study, preplanning was used to help students concentrate on the task at hand. A teacher's total practice is defined by Elias and Schwab (2006)⁷ as the actions they take to create a positive learning environment, regulate daily routines and activities, prevent problems, and remedy them. Pre-service science teachers, according to Gencer and Cakiroglu (2007)⁸, generally held positive efficacy beliefs about

teaching science. In addition, they found that pre-service teachers were instructional managers who intervened in the classroom.

The statement of the problem, in this case

Many different skills are needed for effective teaching, including the ability to adapt one's behaviour in a variety of contexts and situations based on the student's needs at any given time. Classroom management success entails not only effectively responding to problems when they arise, but also preventing problems from recurring. Teachers who want to create a learning community in a tumultuous classroom will need to use the tried-and-true classroom management strategies of articulating clear expectations, implementing preventive and corrective discipline procedures, and modeling and instructing students in the desired behaviours. Recognizing the importance of classroom management, the researcher devised the current study to learn about teachers' current classroom management practices and to develop appropriate classroom management strategies for secondary school teachers. The study's title is "Teacher Attitude towards Classroom Management - A Study in Secondary Schools in Visakhapatnam City)," and it has the following goals.

Objectives

- 1) To study the perceptions of the teachers on various dimensions of management of classroom practices at the secondary schools.
- 2) To find out the impact of demographics of teachers on management of classroom practices.

Hypothesis

1. Demographic of teachers does not determine the dimensions of management of classroom practices at secondary schools.

Methodology

Survey was the method used in this section of the study. It was conducted to find out the impact of in-service teacher training on existing classroom management practices, where the training needs of teachers in relation to the specific management strategies. In addition to the survey conducted, the investigator personally visited certain secondary schools to get deeper information about the physical arrangements and to observe the instructional practices followed by teachers. Additionally, unstructured interviews with educational experts, principals, and senior teachers of secondary schools were conducted to elicit additional information about classroom management practices and the strategies necessary for effective classroom management in secondary schools.

Tools and techniques used in the study

The questionnaire is the main tool in this study. In the present study management of classroom practice questionnaire is a standardized tool used by Rany S. (2007) for her Ph.D. degree. After adopting these two tools from earlier research work the investigator combined together and gone through some modifications and again standardized with critical ration analysis.

Method of Data Collection

The entire teaching faculty at the secondary schools constituted the total population of the study. Since the population is large in size, an optimum sample which faithfully represents the population was selected. Here, the sample consisted of 360 teachers of the secondary schools from the various districts of Visakhapatnam. The technique adopted non-proportional stratified random sampling, where the select sample was divided into subgroups based on gender, age, educational qualification, and experience of teachers, and type of management of school. The sample was based not on the percentage of the subjects in the population presented in each level. The data thus collected were tabulated and subjected to analysis using suitable statistical techniques such as test of significance of difference between means, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and t-tests are used on management of classroom practices.

Data analysis

Table-1: Distribution of sample teachers by their demographic groups

Demographic variables	Groups	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	180	50.0
	Female	180	50.0
Age-group	Below 30 Years	91	25.3
	30-40 Years	141	39.2
	40-50 Years	80	22.2
	Above 50 Years	48	13.3
Professional qualification	D. Ed.	85	23.6
	B. Ed.	167	46.4
	M.Ed.	108	30.0
Designation	Head Masters/ Principal	69	19.2
	School Assistants	159	44.2
	Secondary grade teachers	132	36.6
Teaching experience	Below 10 years	113	31.4
	10-20 years	165	45.8
	Above 20 years	82	22.8
Type of Management	Government	180	50.0
	Private	180	50.0
	Total	360	100.0

Classroom Management Practices

Management of academic calendar is very important factor in classroom practices. While the management of academic calendar organized by the teachers for classroom practices, the perception of the teachers on various plans and preparations in this regard is presented in the following tables.

Table-2: Perceptions of the sample teachers on management of academic calendar with reference to classroom practices

Management of Academic Calendar	Always	Some times	Often	Rarely	Never	Total
1. I have the academic calendar in advance of the start of academic year.	134 (37.2)	102 (28.3)	43 (11.9)	53 (14.7)	28 (7.8)	360 (100.0)
2. Co-curricular activities are designed before the commencement of academic session.	131 (36.4)	126 (35.0)	36 (10.0)	38 (10.6)	29 (8.1)	360 (100.0)
3. Management resource plan is activated before the kick start of the year.	128 (35.6)	97 (26.9)	43 (11.9)	52 (14.4)	40 (11.1)	360 (100.0)
4. Contextual work is planned in advance.	132 (36.7)	109 (30.3)	51 (14.2)	43 (11.9)	25 (6.9)	360 (100.0)
5. Academic years plan for first week is kept ready.	129 (35.8)	119 (33.1)	43 (11.9)	31 (8.6)	38 (10.6)	360 (100.0)

It shows that more than a third of teachers (37.2%) felt always (37.2%) because they prepare a curricular activity plan before the start of the academic year, whereas 28.3 percent felt sometimes, 11.9 percent said often, 14.7 percent opined rarely, and 7.8 percent did not respond. According to the above table, more than a third of teachers felt always (36.4 percent) because they prepare a co-curricular activity plan before the start of the academic year, followed by 35.0 percent who felt sometimes, 10.0 percent who said often, 10.6 percent who said rarely, and 8.1 percent who did not respond. Furthermore, 35.6 percent of teachers agreed management resource plan is activated before the kick start of the year. Whereas 26.9% said sometimes, 11.9 percent said often, 14.4% said rarely, and 11.1 percent did not respond with a statement. According to the above table, more than a third of teachers felt always (36.7 percent) because their contextual work is planned in advance, followed by 30.3 percent who felt sometimes, 14.2 percent who said often, 11.9 percent who said rarely, and 6.9 percent who did not respond. More than a third of teachers (35.8%) said they always feel this way because they plan ahead for the first week of the academic year, whereas 33.1 percent said they feel this way sometimes, 11.9 percent said they feel this way often, 8.6 percent said they feel this way rarely, and 10.6 percent said they don't know.

Table-3: Perceptions of the sample teachers on management of physical arrangements with reference to classroom practices

Management of physical arrangements	Always	Some times	Often	Rarely	Never	Total
1.I plan to put classroom space to appropriate use.	131 (36.4)	102 (28.3)	46 (12.8)	46 (12.8)	35 (9.7)	360 (100.0)
2.I change the seating arrangement as per my instruction method.	122 (33.9)	109 (30.3)	54 (15.0)	33 (9.2)	42 (11.7)	360 (100.0)
3.In my classroom provision for technology laboratory is separate.	147 (40.8)	110 (30.6)	45 (12.5)	33 (9.2)	25 (6.9)	360 (100.0)
4.A living corner is made in my class.	128 (35.6)	95 (26.4)	52 (14.4)	39 (10.8)	46 (12.8)	360 (100.0)
5.I make sure of a comfortable classroom.	146 (40.6)	83 (23.1)	47 (13.1)	33 (9.2)	51 (14.2)	360 (100.0)

It shows that more than thirty percent of the teachers opinioned always (36.4%) for they put classroom space to appropriate use, whereas 28.3 percent felt sometimes, 12.8 percent said often, 12.8 percent opined rarely and 9.7 percent not responded with the statement. In the above table explains that one-third of the teachers perceived always (33.9%) for they change the seating arrangement as per their instruction method, followed by 30.3 percent felt sometimes, 15.0 percent said often, 9.2 percent opined rarely and 11.7 percent not responded with this. On the other hand forty percent of the teachers (40.8%) opined in their class provision for technology laboratory is separate, whereas 30.6 percent felt sometimes, 12.5 percent said often, 9.2 percent opined rarely and 6.9 percent not responded with the statement. In the above table explains that more than thirty percent of the teachers perceived always (35.6%) for they arrange a living corner in the class, followed by 26.4 percent felt sometimes, 14.4 percent said often, 10.8 percent opined rarely and 12.8 percent not responded with the statement. And forty percent of the teachers (40.6%) opined always for they arrange a total comfort in their classroom, whereas 23.1 percent felt sometimes, 13.1 percent said often, 9.2 percent opined rarely and 14.2 percent not responded with the statement.

Table-4: Perceptions of the sample teachers on behaviour management with reference to classroom practices

Behaviour management	Always	Some times	Often	Rarely	Never	Total
1. For instructing and maintaining discipline in classroom rules are very important.	133 (36.9)	100 (27.8)	66 (18.3)	27 (7.5)	34 (9.4)	360 (100.0)
2. I use power base appropriately as per situation in classroom and nature of students.	126 (35.0)	105 (29.2)	63 (17.5)	32 (8.9)	34 (9.4)	360 (100.0)
3. My discipline models are selected as per situation in classroom and nature of students.	131 (36.4)	97 (26.9)	62 (17.2)	37 (10.3)	33 (9.2)	360 (100.0)
4. Necessary steps are taken by me to maintain rapport with parents.	129 (35.8)	111 (30.8)	60 (16.7)	29 (8.1)	31 (8.6)	360 (100.0)
5. Behavioural problems in students I solve through behavior contracts.	133 (36.9)	94 (26.1)	75 (20.8)	34 (9.4)	24 (6.7)	360 (100.0)

The above table indicates that more than thirty percent of the teachers opined always (36.9%) for they consider for instructing and maintaining discipline classroom rules are important, whereas 27.8 percent felt sometimes, 18.3 percent said often, 7.5 percent opined rarely and 9.4 percent not responded with the statement. In the above table explains that more than thirty percent of the teachers perceived always (35.0%) for they use power base appropriately as per situation in classroom and nature of students, followed by 29.2 percent felt sometimes, 17.5 percent said often, 8.9 percent opined rarely and 9.4 percent not responded with this. It infers that 36.4 percent of the teachers opined always their discipline models are selected as per the situation in classroom and nature of students, whereas 26.9 percent felt sometimes, 17.2 percent said often, 10.3 percent opined rarely and 9.2 percent not responded with the statement. In the above table explains that more than thirty percent of the teachers perceived always (35.8%) for taking necessary steps by them to maintain rapport with parents, followed by 30.8 percent felt sometimes, 16.7 percent said often, 8.1 percent opined rarely and 8.6 percent not responded with the statement. More than thirty percent of the teachers (36.9%) opined always as they solve problems of behavior in students they solve through behavior contracts, whereas 26.1 percent felt sometimes, 20.8 percent said often, 9.4 percent opined rarely and 6.7 percent not responded with the statement.

Table–5: Perceptions of the sample teachers on instructional management with reference to classroom practices

Instructional management	Always	Some times	Often	Rarely	Never	Total
1. Instructional plans are different which I follow in my class.	137 (38.1)	91 (25.3)	69 (19.2)	32 (8.9)	31 (8.6)	360 (100.0)
2. I practice individualized instruction techniques in my class.	137 (38.1)	92 (25.6)	62 (17.2)	40 (11.1)	29 (8.1)	360 (100.0)
3. I utilize all available resources for transacting 4. Pedagogy.	128 (35.6)	103 (28.6)	69 (19.2)	31 (8.6)	29 (8.1)	360 (100.0)
5. I practice group instructional methods in my classroom teaching.	140 (38.9)	90 (25.0)	69 (19.2)	30 (8.3)	31 (8.6)	360 (100.0)

The above table represents that nearly forty percent of the teachers opined always (38.1%) for they practice different types of instructional plans in the class, whereas 25.3 percent felt sometimes, 19.2 percent said often, 8.9 percent opined rarely and 8.6 percent not responded with the statement. In the above table explains that 38.1 percent of the teachers perceived always for they practice individualized instruction techniques in the class, followed by 25.6 percent felt sometimes, 17.2 percent said often, 11.1 percent opined rarely and 8.1 percent not responded with this. According to the data it shows that 35.6 percent of the teachers opined always for they utilize all available resources for transacting Pedagogy, whereas 28.6 percent felt sometimes, 19.2 percent said often, 8.6 percent opined rarely and 8.1 percent not responded with the statement. In the above table explains that nearly forty percent of the teachers perceived always (38.9%) for they practice group instructional methods in the classroom teaching, followed by 25.0 percent felt sometimes, 19.2 percent said often, 8.3 percent opined rarely and 8.6 percent not responded with the statement.

Table–6: Perceptions of the sample teachers on evaluation management with reference to classroom practices

Evaluation management	Always	Some times	Often	Rarely	Never	Total
1.Assessment of students is done on a continual and comprehensive basis in my class.	131 (36.4)	95 (26.4)	55 (15.3)	42 (11.7)	37 (10.3)	360 (100.0)
2.I encourage students for peer evaluation.	143 (39.7)	88 (24.4)	61 (16.9)	30 (8.3)	38 (10.6)	360 (100.0)
3.I encourage parents in student evaluation	140 (38.9)	98 (27.2)	53 (14.7)	34 (9.4)	35 (9.7)	360 (100.0)
4.I encourage students in teacher evaluation.	133 (36.9)	99 (27.5)	64 (17.8)	32 (8.9)	32 (8.9)	360 (100.0)
5.I practice peer evaluation for professional growth.	136 (37.8)	96 (26.7)	59 (16.4)	36 (10.0)	33 (9.2)	360 (100.0)

The above table represents that more than thirty percent of the teachers opined always (36.4%) for they assess the students on a continual and on a comprehensive basis, whereas 26.4 percent felt sometimes, 15.3 percent said often, 11.7 percent opined rarely and 10.3 percent not responded with the statement. In the above table explains that 39.1 percent of the teachers perceived always for they encourage students for peer evaluation, followed by 24.4 percent felt sometimes, 16.9 percent said often, 8.3 percent opined rarely and 10.6 percent not responded with this. The data infers that 38.9 percent of the teachers opined always for they encourage parents in student evaluation, whereas 27.2 percent felt sometimes, 14.7 percent said often, 9.4 percent opined rarely and 9.7 percent not responded with the statement. In the above table explains that 36.9 percent of the teachers perceived always for encourage students in teacher evaluation, followed by 27.5 percent felt sometimes, 17.8 percent said often, 8.9 percent opined rarely and 8.9 percent not responded with the statement. Out of the total sample more than thirty percent of the teachers (37.8%) opined always for they practice peer evaluation for professional growth, whereas 26.7 percent felt sometimes, 16.4 percent said often, 10.0 percent opined rarely and 9.2 percent not responded with the statement.

Table–7: Perceptions of the sample teachers on management of students with reference to classroom practices

Student management	Always	Some times	Often	Rarely	Never	Total
1. On a collective basis with my students certain classroom rules are set up.	127 (35.3)	106 (29.4)	48 (13.3)	42 (11.7)	37 (10.3)	360 (100.0)
2. I use my power base as per my students nature.	135 (37.5)	90 (25.0)	67 (18.6)	33 (9.2)	35 (9.7)	360 (100.0)
3. I follow discipline models as per my students.	134 (37.2)	88 (24.4)	68 (18.9)	30 (8.3)	40 (11.1)	360 (100.0)
4. Students with positive behavior are praised immediately.	137 (38.1)	81 (22.5)	60 (16.7)	41 (11.4)	41 (11.4)	360 (100.0)
5. I help my students with disruptive behavior in framing a workable plan.	145 (40.3)	105 (29.2)	48 (13.3)	30 (8.3)	32 (8.9)	360 (100.0)

According to the above table, more than three-quarters of teachers (35.3%) felt always, 13.3% said often, 11.7 percent said rarely, and 10.3 percent did not respond with a statement, whereas 29.4% felt sometimes, 13.3% said often, 11.7 percent said rarely, and 10.3 percent did not respond with a statement. According to the above table, 37.5 percent of teachers felt always because they use different teacher power bases depending on the nature of their students, followed by 25.0 percent who felt sometimes, 18.6 percent who said often, 9.2 percent who said rarely, and 9.7 percent who did not respond. According to the data, 37.2 percent of teachers felt always because they use different discipline models depending on the nature of their students, whereas 24.4 percent felt occasionally, 18.9 percent said often, 8.3 percent said rarely, and 11.1 percent did not respond. According to the above table, 38.1 percent of teachers believe they give praise immediately after a positive student behaviour, followed by 22.5 percent who believe they do so occasionally, 16.7% who believe they do so frequently, 11.4 percent who believe they do so rarely, and 11.4 percent who do not respond to the statement. Out of the total sample, 40.3 percent of teachers said they always help students develop a workable plan for changing disruptive behaviour, while 29.2 percent said sometimes, 13.3 percent said often, 8.3 percent said rarely, and 8.9 percent did not respond with the statement. It shows that 36.7 percent of teachers said they always take care of students during individual problem solving, while 31.4 percent said sometimes, 15.8 percent said often, 7.8 percent said rarely, and 8.3 percent said they don't know.

Table–8: Perceptions of the sample teachers on classroom management with reference to classroom practices

Classroom management	Always	Some times	Often	Rarely	Never	Total
1. I keep a check on reviewing rules.	132 (36.7)	97 (26.9)	57 (15.8)	33 (9.2)	41 (11.4)	360 (100.0)
2. I adopt neutrality principle in classroom management.	144 (40.0)	90 (25.0)	58 (16.1)	32 (8.9)	36 (10.01)	360 (100.0)
3. I avoid corporal punishment in my class.	126 (35.0)	94 (26.1)	62 (17.2)	35 (9.7)	43 (11.9)	360 (100.0)
4. First parent meeting is conducted within 5 days of the start of academic year.	127 (35.3)	100 (27.8)	64 (17.8)	31 (8.6)	38 (10.6)	360 (100.0)
5. Parental support is appreciated in classroom management.	128 (35.6)	99 (27.5)	54 (15.0)	43 (11.9)	36 (10.0)	360 (100.0)

The above table represents that more than thirty percent of the teachers opined always (36.7%) for they take care in monitoring and reviewing rules, whereas 26.9 percent felt sometimes, 15.8 percent said often, 9.2 percent opined rarely and 11.4 percent not responded with the statement. In the above table explains that forty percent of the teachers perceived always for they adopt non-interventionist principle for classroom management, followed by 25.0 percent felt sometimes, 16.1 percent said often, 8.9 percent opined rarely and 10.0 percent not responded with this. It also shows that 35.0 percent of the teachers opined always for they avoid corporal punishment in the class, whereas 26.1 percent felt sometimes, 17.2 percent said often, 9.7 percent opined rarely and 11.9 percent not responded with the statement. In the above table explains that 35.3 percent of the teachers perceived they welcome parents at the beginning of the academic year with a meeting, followed by 27.8 percent felt sometimes, 17.8 percent said often, 8.6 percent opined rarely and 10.6 percent not responded with the statement. And finally more than thirty percent of the teachers (35.6%) opined the parental support is appreciated in classroom management, whereas 27.5 percent felt sometimes, 15.0 percent said often, 11.9 percent opined rarely and 10.0 percent not responded with the statement.

Table–9: Perceptions of male and female teachers on management of classroom practices

Factors	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
Management of Academic Calendar	Male	180	36.59	4.675	0.348	0.367	0.714
	Female	180	36.77	4.794	0.357		
Management of Physical arrangements	Male	180	36.69	4.805	0.358	0.276	0.783
	Female	180	36.82	4.340	0.323		
Behaviour management	Male	180	37.01	8.207	0.611	0.434	0.665
	Female	180	37.37	7.314	0.545		
Instructional Management	Male	180	37.08	10.514	0.783	0.163	0.871
	Female	180	37.26	10.191	0.759		
Evaluation management	Male	180	37.13	11.208	0.835	0.063	0.950
	Female	180	37.20	10.459	0.779		
Management of students	Male	180	37.16	9.610	0.716	0.006	0.996
	Female	180	37.15	9.235	0.688		
Classroom management	Male	180	36.52	10.046	0.748	0.114	0.910
	Female	180	36.41	9.425	0.702		

The table compares and contrasts male and female teachers' views on classroom practices in secondary schools in the study area. Female teachers have a higher average perception score of 36.77 than male teachers when it comes to managing the academic calendar in the classroom (36.59). Because the p-value is 0.714, the calculated t-value of 0.367 is not significant.

This implies that there is no significant difference in male and female teachers' perceptions of how to manage the academic calendar in the classroom. Female teachers have a higher average perception score (36.82) than male teachers when it comes to physical arrangement classroom practices (36.69).

Because the p-value is 0.783, the calculated t-value of 0.276 indicates that the result is not significant. This suggests that there is no significant difference in male and female teachers' perceptions of how to manage physical arrangements in the classroom.

Female teachers have a higher average perception score on classroom behaviour management practices than male teachers, with a score of 37.37. (37.01). because the p-value is 0.665, the calculated t-value of 0.434 is not significant. This implies that there is no significant difference in perceptions of classroom behaviour management practices between male and female teachers.

In terms of instructional management classroom practices, female teachers had a higher average perception score (37.26) than male teachers (37.08). Because the p-value is 0.871, the calculated t-value of 0.163 indicates that the result is not significant. This implies that there is no significant difference in perceptions of instructional management in classroom practices between male and female teachers.

It shows that female teachers have a higher average perception score on evaluation management classroom practices (37.20) than male teachers (37.13). Because the p-value is 0.950, the calculated t-value of 0.063 is not significant.

This implies that there is no significant difference in perceptions of evaluation management classroom practices between male and female teachers. In terms of student classroom management, male teachers had a slightly higher average perception score (37.16) than female teachers (37.15).

Because the p-value is 0.996, the calculated t-value of 0.006 indicates that the result is not significant. This implies that there is no significant difference in perceptions of student management in classroom practices between male and female teachers.

It implies that male teachers have a higher average perception score of classroom management in classroom practices (36.52) than female teachers (36.41). Because the p-value is 0.910, the calculated t-value of 0.114 indicates that the result is not significant. This implies that there is no significant difference in perceptions of classroom management in classroom practices between male and female teachers.

Table–10: Perceptions of teachers on the management of classroom practices by their age-group

Factors	Age in years	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Std. Error	f-value	p-value
Management of Academic Calendar	Below 30 Years	91	36.61	4.506	0.472	0.132	0.941
	30-40 Years	141	36.54	5.181	0.436		
	40-50 Years	80	36.85	4.158	0.464		
	Above 50 Years	48	36.95	4.771	0.688		
	Total	360	36.68	4.729	0.249		
Management of Physical arrangements	Below 30 Years	91	36.19	4.551	0.477	2.404	0.067
	30-40 Years	141	37.48	4.428	0.372		
	40-50 Years	80	36.70	4.401	0.492		
	Above 50 Years	48	35.79	5.090	0.734		
	Total	360	36.76	4.572	0.241		
Behaviour management	Below 30 Years	91	37.78	7.666	0.803	1.844	0.139
	30-40 Years	141	37.48	7.700	0.648		
	40-50 Years	80	37.46	8.216	0.918		
	Above 50 Years	48	34.77	7.131	1.029		
	Total	360	37.19	7.765	0.409		
Instructional Management	Below 30 Years	91	37.59	10.885	1.141	2.015	0.111
	30-40 Years	141	37.92	9.817	0.826		
	40-50 Years	80	37.38	10.583	1.183		
	Above 50 Years	48	33.81	10.037	1.448		
	Total	360	37.17	10.340	0.544		
Evaluation management	Below 30 Years	91	37.61	11.173	1.171	1.398	0.243
	30-40 Years	141	37.99	10.571	0.890		
	40-50 Years	80	36.87	11.105	1.241		
	Above 50 Years	48	34.39	10.268	1.482		
	Total	360	37.16	10.825	0.570		
Management of students	Below 30 Years	91	37.65	9.307	0.975	1.033	0.378
	30-40 Years	141	37.60	9.386	0.790		
	40-50 Years	80	37.10	10.333	1.155		
	Above 50 Years	48	35.00	7.938	1.145		
	Total	360	37.15	9.411	0.496		
Classroom management	Below 30 Years	91	36.67	10.153	1.064	1.440	0.231
	30-40 Years	141	37.24	9.190	0.774		
	40-50 Years	80	36.41	10.134	1.133		
	Above 50 Years	48	33.89	9.616	1.388		
	Total	360	36.46	9.727	0.512		

The table analyses the difference between different age group teachers in their perceptions on classroom practices in secondary schools of study area. It is found that the average perception score of above 50 years age group teachers on management of academic calendar classroom practices is 36.95 found higher than 40-50 years age group teachers (36.85), 30-40 year age group teachers (36.54) and below 30 years age group teachers (36.61). The calculated f-value

0.132 is not significant because the p-value is 0.941. This infers that there is no significant difference between different age group teachers in their perceptions on management of academic calendar classroom practices.

Regarding management of physical arrangement classroom practices the average perception score of 30-40 years age group teachers (37.48) found higher than less than 30 years age group teachers (36.19), 40-50 year age group teachers (36.70) and above 50 years age group teachers (35.79). Here the calculated f-value 2.404 indicates not significant because the p-value is 0.067. This can be inferred that there is no significant difference between different age group teachers in their perceptions on management of physical arrangements in classroom practices.

It is found that the average perception score of below 30 years age group teachers on behaviour management classroom practices is 37.78 found higher than 30-40 years age group teachers (37.48), 40-50 year age group teachers (37.46) and above 50 years age group teachers (34.77). The calculated f-value 1.844 is not significant because the p-value is 0.139. This infers that there is no significant difference between different age group teachers in their perceptions on behaviour management classroom practices.

Regarding instructional management classroom practices the average perception score of 30-40 years age group teachers (37.92) found higher than less than 30 years age group teachers (37.59), 40-50 year age group teachers (37.38) and above 50 years age group teachers (33.81). Here the calculated f-value 2.015 indicates not significant because the p-value is 0.111. This can be inferred that there is no significant difference between different age group teachers in their perceptions on instructional management in classroom practices.

It shows that the average perception score of 30-40 years age group teachers on evaluation management classroom practices is 37.99 found higher than below 30 years age group teachers (37.61), 40-50 year age group teachers (36.87) and above 50 years age group teachers (34.39). The calculated f-value 1.398 is not significant because the p-value is 0.243. This infers that there is no significant difference between different age group teachers in their perceptions on evaluation management classroom practices.

Regarding management of student's classroom practices the average perception score of less than 30 years age group teachers (37.65) found higher than 30-40 years age group teachers (37.60), 40-50 year age group teachers (37.10) and above 50 years age group teachers (35.00). Here the calculated f-value 1.033 indicates not significant because the p-value is 0.378. This can be inferred that there is no significant difference between different age group teachers in their perceptions on management of students in classroom practices.

It infers that the classroom management in classroom practices the average perception score of 30-40 years age group teachers (37.24) found higher than less than 30 years age group teachers (37.24), 40-50 year age group teachers (36.41) and above 50 years age group teachers (33.89). Here the calculated f-value 1.440 indicates not significant because the p-value is 0.231. This

can be inferred that there is no significant difference between different age group teachers in their perceptions on classroom management in classroom practices.

Table–11: Perceptions of teachers on the management of classroom practices by their professional qualification

Factors	Professional qualification	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Std. Error	f-value	p-value
Management of Academic Calendar	D. Ed.	85	36.16	4.550	0.493	0.700	0.497
	B. Ed.	167	36.89	4.642	0.359		
	M.Ed.	108	36.76	5.007	0.481		
	Total	360	36.68	4.729	0.249		
Management of Physical arrangements	D. Ed.	85	36.50	4.500	0.488	0.679	0.508
	B. Ed.	167	36.61	4.781	0.370		
	M.Ed.	108	37.18	4.304	0.414		
	Total	360	36.76	4.572	0.241		
Behaviour management	D. Ed.	85	36.56	7.396	0.802	0.405	0.667
	B. Ed.	167	37.28	8.021	0.620		
	M.Ed.	108	37.55	7.685	0.739		
	Total	360	37.19	7.765	0.409		
Instructional Management	D. Ed.	85	36.35	10.108	1.096	0.412	0.662
	B. Ed.	167	37.24	10.318	0.798		
	M.Ed.	108	37.70	10.607	1.020		
	Total	360	37.17	10.340	0.544		
Evaluation management	D. Ed.	85	36.35	10.741	1.165	0.368	0.692
	B. Ed.	167	37.25	10.899	0.843		
	M.Ed.	108	37.68	10.839	1.043		
	Total	360	37.16	10.825	0.570		
Management of students	D. Ed.	85	36.36	8.754	0.949	0.394	0.674
	B. Ed.	167	37.41	9.394	0.726		
	M.Ed.	108	37.38	9.973	0.959		
	Total	360	37.15	9.411	0.496		
Classroom management	D. Ed.	85	36.18	9.203	0.998	0.064	0.938
	B. Ed.	167	36.46	9.856	0.762		
	M.Ed.	108	36.69	10.008	0.963		
	Total	360	36.46	9.727	0.512		

The table analyses the difference between different levels of professional qualification of teachers in their perceptions on classroom practices in secondary schools of study area. It is found that the average perception score of B.Ed. qualified teachers on management of academic calendar classroom practices is 36.89 found higher than M.Ed. holders (36.76) and D.Ed. qualified teachers (36.16). The calculated f-value 0.700 is not significant because the p-value

is 0.497. This infers that there is no significant difference between different professional qualifications of teachers in their perceptions on management of academic calendar classroom practices.

Regarding management of physical arrangement classroom practices the average perception score of M.Ed. qualified teachers on classroom practices is 37.18 found higher than B.Ed. holders (36.61) and D.Ed. qualified teachers (36.50). Here the calculated f-value 0.679 indicates not significant because the p-value is 0.508. This can be inferred that there is no significant difference between different professional qualifications of teachers in their perceptions on management of physical arrangements in classroom practices.

It is found that the average perception score of M.Ed. holders on behaviour management classroom practices is 37.55 found higher than B.Ed. holders (37.28) and D.Ed. qualified teachers (36.56). The calculated f-value 0.405 is not significant because the p-value is 0.667. This infers that there is no significant difference between different professional qualifications of teachers in their perceptions on behaviour management classroom practices.

Regarding instructional management classroom practices the average perception score of M.Ed. holders on classroom practices is 37.70 found higher than B.Ed. (37.24) and D.Ed. qualified teachers (36.35). Here the calculated f-value 0.412 indicates not significant because the p-value is 0.662. This can be inferred that there is no significant difference between professional qualifications of teachers in their perceptions on instructional management in classroom practices.

It shows that the average perception score of M.Ed. qualified teachers on evaluation management classroom practices is 37.68 found higher than B.Ed. (37.25) and D.Ed. qualified teachers (36.35). The calculated f-value 0.368 is not significant because the p-value is 0.692. This infers that there is no significant difference between different levels of professional qualifications of teachers in their perceptions on evaluation management classroom practices.

Regarding management of students classroom practices the average perception score B.Ed. qualified teachers on classroom practices is 37.41 found higher than M.Ed. (37.38) and D.Ed. qualified teachers (36.36). Here the calculated f-value 0.394 indicates not significant because the p-value is 0.674. This can be inferred that there is no significant difference between different professional qualification levels of teachers in their perceptions on management of students in classroom practices.

It infers that the classroom management in classroom practices the average perception score of M.Ed. qualified teachers (36.69) found higher than B.Ed. (36.46) and D.Ed. qualified teachers (36.18). Here the calculated f-value 0.064 indicates not significant because the p-value is 0.938. This can be inferred that there is no significant difference between different professional qualifications of teachers in their perceptions on classroom management in classroom practices.

Table–12: Perceptions of teachers on the management of classroom practices by their designation

Factors	Designation	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Std. Error	f-value	p-value
Management of Academic Calendar	Head Masters	69	36.52	5.028	0.605	0.072	0.930
	School Assistants	159	36.67	4.407	0.349		
	Secondary grade teachers	132	36.78	4.973	0.432		
	Total	360	36.68	4.729	0.249		
Management of Physical arrangements	Head Masters	69	36.42	4.138	0.498	0.236	0.790
	School Assistants	159	36.84	4.840	0.383		
	Secondary grade teachers	132	36.83	4.480	0.390		
	Total	360	36.76	4.572	0.241		
Behaviour management	Head Masters	69	37.05	7.366	0.886	0.197	0.821
	School Assistants	159	36.97	8.052	0.638		
	Secondary grade teachers	132	37.53	7.661	0.666		
	Total	360	37.19	7.765	0.409		
Instructional Management	Head Masters	69	37.21	10.278	1.237	0.050	0.951
	School Assistants	159	36.98	10.352	0.820		
	Secondary grade teachers	132	37.37	10.432	0.908		
	Total	360	37.17	10.340	0.544		
Evaluation management	Head Masters	69	37.36	10.524	1.266	0.024	0.976
	School Assistants	159	37.20	11.058	0.877		
	Secondary grade teachers	132	37.02	10.775	0.937		
	Total	360	37.16	10.825	0.570		
Management of students	Head Masters	69	37.21	9.076	1.092	0.139	0.871
	School Assistants	159	36.88	9.554	0.757		
	Secondary grade teachers	132	37.46	9.471	0.824		
	Total	360	37.15	9.411	0.496		
Classroom management	Head Masters	69	36.57	9.060	1.090	0.006	0.994
	School Assistants	159	36.43	9.751	0.773		
	Secondary grade teachers	132	36.45	10.099	0.879		
	Total	360	36.46	9.727	0.512		

The table analyses the difference between designations of teachers in their perceptions on classroom practices in secondary schools of study area. It is found that the average perception score of secondary grade teachers on management of academic calendar classroom practices is 36.78 found higher than school assistants (36.67) and Head Masters (36.52). The calculated f-value 0.072 is not significant because the p-value is 0.930. This infers that there is no significant difference between designations of teachers in their perceptions on management of academic calendar classroom practices.

Regarding management of physical arrangement classroom practices the average perception score of school assistants on classroom practices is 36.84 found higher than secondary grade teachers (36.83) and Head Masters (36.42). Here the calculated f-value 0.236 indicates not significant because the p-value is 0.790. This can be inferred that there is no significant difference between designations of teachers in their perceptions on management of physical arrangements in classroom practices.

It is found that the average perception score of secondary grade teachers on behaviour management classroom practices is 37.53 found higher than Head Masters (37.05) and school assistants (36.97). The calculated f-value 0.197 is not significant because the p-value is 0.821. This infers that there is no significant difference between designations of teachers in their perceptions on behaviour management classroom practices.

Regarding instructional management classroom practices the average perception score of secondary grade teachers on classroom practices is 37.37 found higher than Head Masters (37.21) and school assistants (36.98). Here the calculated f-value 0.050 indicates not significant because the p-value is 0.951. This can be inferred that there is no significant difference between designations of teachers in their perceptions on instructional management in classroom practices.

It shows that the average perception score of Head masters on evaluation management classroom practices is 37.36 found higher than school assistants (37.20) and secondary grade teachers (37.02). The calculated f-value 0.024 is not significant because the p-value is 0.976. This infers that there is no significant difference between designations of teachers in their perceptions on evaluation management classroom practices.

Regarding management of students classroom practices the average perception score of secondary grade teachers on classroom practices is 37.46 found higher than Head Masters (37.21) and school assistants (36.88). Here the calculated f-value 0.139 indicates not significant because the p-value is 0.871. This can be inferred that there is no significant difference between designations of teachers in their perceptions on management of students in classroom practices.

It infers that the classroom management in classroom practices the average perception score of Head masters are 37.57 found higher than secondary grade teachers (36.45) and school assistants (36.43). Here the calculated f-value 0.006 indicates not significant because the p-value is 0.994. This can be inferred that there is no significant difference between teachers designations in their perceptions on classroom management in classroom practices.

Table–13: Perceptions of teachers on the management of classroom practices by their teaching experience (in years)

Factors	Teaching experience	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Std. Error	f-value	p-value
Management of Academic Calendar	Below 10 years	113	36.45	4.503	0.423	0.438	0.646
	10-20 years	165	36.93	4.893	0.380		
	Above 20 years	82	36.50	4.730	0.522		
	Total	360	36.68	4.729	0.249		
Management of Physical arrangements	Below 10 years	113	36.87	4.377	0.411	0.080	0.923
	10-20 years	165	36.75	4.818	0.375		
	Above 20 years	82	36.60	4.373	0.483		
	Total	360	36.76	4.572	0.241		
Behaviour management	Below 10 years	113	38.20	6.883	0.647	1.498	0.225
	10-20 years	165	36.89	7.940	0.618		
	Above 20 years	82	36.41	8.476	0.936		
	Total	360	37.19	7.765	0.409		
Instructional Management	Below 10 years	113	38.15	9.592	0.902	0.826	0.439
	10-20 years	165	36.92	10.641	0.828		
	Above 20 years	82	36.32	10.731	1.185		
	Total	360	37.17	10.340	0.544		
Evaluation management	Below 10 years	113	38.35	10.112	0.951	1.079	0.341
	10-20 years	165	36.83	10.999	0.856		
	Above 20 years	82	36.20	11.397	1.258		
	Total	360	37.16	10.825	0.570		
Management of students	Below 10 years	113	38.79	8.788	0.826	2.530	0.081
	10-20 years	165	36.47	9.438	0.734		
	Above 20 years	82	36.26	9.998	1.104		
	Total	360	37.15	9.411	0.496		
Classroom management	Below 10 years	113	37.62	8.957	0.842	1.367	0.256
	10-20 years	165	36.21	10.107	0.786		
	Above 20 years	82	35.39	9.921	1.095		
	Total	360	36.46	9.727	0.512		

The table analyses the difference between different experiences levels of teachers in their perceptions on classroom practices in secondary schools of study area. It is found that the average perception score of 10-20 years experienced teachers on management of academic calendar classroom practices is 36.93 found higher than above 20 years (36.50) and below 10 years experienced teachers (36.45). The calculated f-value 0.438 is not significant because the p-value is 0.646. This infers that there is no significant difference between different experiences levels of teachers in their perceptions on management of academic calendar classroom practices.

Regarding management of physical arrangement classroom practices the average perception score of below 10 years experienced teachers is 36.87 found higher than 10-20 years (36.75) and above 20 years experienced teachers (36.60). Here the calculated f-value 0.080 indicates not significant because the p-value is 0.923. This can be inferred that there is no significant difference between different experiences levels of teachers in their perceptions on management of physical arrangements in classroom practices.

It is inferred that the average perception below 10 years experienced teachers on behaviour management classroom practices is 38.20 found higher than 10-20 years (36.89) and above 20 years experienced teachers (36.41). The calculated f-value 1.498 is not significant because the p-value is 0.225. This infers that there is no significant difference between different experiences levels of teachers in their perceptions on behaviour management classroom practices.

Whereas, instructional management classroom practices the average perception score of below 10 years experienced teachers are 38.15 found higher than 10-20 years (36.92) and above 20 years experienced teachers (36.32). Here the calculated f-value 0.826 indicates not significant because the p-value is 0.439. This can be inferred that there is no significant difference between different experiences levels of teachers in their perceptions on instructional management in classroom practices.

It is inferred that the average perception score of below 10 years experienced teachers on evaluation management classroom practices is 38.35 found higher than 10-20 years (36.83) and above 20 years experienced teachers (36.20). The calculated f-value 1.079 is not significant because the p-value is 0.341. This infers that there is no significant difference between different experiences levels of teachers in their perceptions on evaluation management classroom practices.

Regarding management of student's classroom practices the average perception score of below 10 years experienced teachers are 38.79 found higher than 10-20 years (36.47) and above 20 years experienced teachers (36.26). Here the calculated f-value 2.530 indicates not significant because the p-value is 0.081. This can be inferred that there is no significant difference between different experiences levels of teachers in their perceptions on management of students in classroom practices.

It is observed that the classroom management in classroom practices the average perception score of below 10 years experienced teachers are 37.62 found higher than 10-20 years (36.21) and above 20 years experienced teachers (35.39). Here the calculated f-value 1.367 indicates not significant because the p-value is 0.256. This can be inferred that there is no significant difference between different experiences levels of teachers in their perceptions on classroom management in classroom practices.

Table–14: Perceptions of government and private management teachers on the management of classroom practices

Factors	Type of Management	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
Management of Academic Calendar	Government	180	35.66	4.682	0.348	4.182**	0.000
	Private	180	37.70	4.566	0.340		
Management of Physical arrangements	Government	180	37.39	4.119	0.307	2.650**	0.008
	Private	180	36.12	4.916	0.366		
Behaviour management	Government	180	37.03	7.977	0.594	0.393	0.694
	Private	180	37.35	7.565	0.563		
Instructional Management	Government	180	37.02	10.354	0.771	0.275	0.784
	Private	180	37.32	10.352	0.771		
Evaluation management	Government	180	37.60	10.855	0.809	0.754	0.451
	Private	180	36.73	10.807	0.805		
Management of students	Government	180	36.29	9.120	0.679	1.746	0.082
	Private	180	38.02	9.642	0.718		
Classroom management	Government	180	36.44	9.512	0.709	0.049	0.961
	Private	180	36.49	9.964	0.742		

**Significant at 1% level.

The table compares and contrasts male and female teachers' views on classroom practices in secondary schools in the study area. Female teachers have a higher average perception score of 36.77 than male teachers when it comes to managing the academic calendar in the classroom (36.59). Because the p-value is 0.714, the calculated t-value of 0.367 is not significant. This implies that there is no significant difference in male and female teachers' perceptions of how to manage the academic calendar in the classroom.

Female teachers have a higher average perception score (36.82) than male teachers when it comes to physical arrangement classroom practices (36.69). Because the p-value is 0.783, the calculated t-value of 0.276 indicates that the result is not significant. This suggests that there is no significant difference in male and female teachers' perceptions of how to manage physical arrangements in the classroom.

Female teachers have a higher average perception score on classroom behaviour management practices than male teachers, with a score of 37.37. (37.01). because the p-value is 0.665, the calculated t-value of 0.434 is not significant. This implies that there is no significant difference in perceptions of classroom behaviour management practices between male and female teachers.

In terms of instructional management classroom practices, female teachers had a higher average perception score (37.26) than male teachers (37.08). Because the p-value is 0.871, the calculated t-value of 0.163 indicates that the result is not significant. This implies that there is

no significant difference in perceptions of instructional management in classroom practices between male and female teachers.

It shows that female teachers have a higher average perception score on evaluation management classroom practices (37.20) than male teachers (37.13). Because the p-value is 0.950, the calculated t-value of 0.063 is not significant. This implies that there is no significant difference in perceptions of evaluation management classroom practices between male and female teachers.

In terms of student classroom management, male teachers had a slightly higher average perception score (37.16) than female teachers (37.15). Because the p-value is 0.996, the calculated t-value of 0.006 indicates that the result is not significant. This implies that there is no significant difference in perceptions of student management in classroom practices between male and female teachers.

It implies that male teachers have a higher average perception score of classroom management in classroom practices (36.52) than female teachers (36.41). Because the p-value is 0.910, the calculated t-value of 0.114 indicates that the result is not significant. This implies that there is no significant difference in perceptions of classroom management in classroom practices between male and female teachers.

Findings

1. According to the above analysis, female teachers are more positive in the classroom when it comes to managing the academic calendar, physical arrangements, behaviour management, instructional management, and evaluation management. When it comes to student management and classroom management in classroom practices, male teachers are more positive than female teachers.
2. It has been discovered that teachers in the 30-40 year age group are more positive than teachers in other age groups when it comes to physical arrangements, instructional management, evaluation management, and classroom management in classroom practices. Teachers in the under-30 age group, on the other hand, are more optimistic about behaviour management and student classroom practices than teachers in other age groups. Teachers in the 50+ age group are more optimistic than teachers in other age groups when it comes to managing the academic calendar in the classroom.
3. In terms of physical arrangements, behaviour management, instructional management, evaluation management, and classroom management, M.Ed. qualified teachers are more positive than B. Ed. and D. Ed. qualified teachers. Whereas, B.Ed. qualified teachers are more positive than M.Ed. and D.Ed. qualified teachers towards management of academic calendar and management of students in classroom practices.
4. It can be concluded that secondary grade teachers are more positive than school assistants and Head Masters regarding management of academic calendar, behaviour

management, instructional management, and management of students in the classroom practices. Whereas, Head Masters are more positive than school assistants and secondary grade teachers towards evaluation and classroom management in classroom practices. With regards school assistants are more positive than secondary grade teachers and Head Masters regarding management of physical arrangements in classroom practices.

5. Teachers with less than ten years of experience are more positive than teachers with ten to twenty years of experience in terms of physical arrangements, behaviour management, instructional management, evaluation management, student management, and classroom management. Teachers with 10-20 years of experience are more optimistic than teachers with less experience about managing the academic calendar in the classroom.
6. In terms of academic calendar management, behaviour management, instructional management, student management, and classroom management, private school teachers are more positive than government school teachers. Government school teachers, on the other hand, are more optimistic about managing physical arrangements and evaluating management in classroom practices than private school teachers.

Conclusion

To summarise, teachers must be aware of a variety of factors that influence the classroom environment and support the teaching-learning process, such as academic calendar management, physical arrangements management, behaviour management, instructional management, evaluation management, student management, and classroom management. The primary responsibility of a teacher in a classroom is to promote behavioural competence and facilitate learning for all students. If teachers provide guidance for effective classroom performance, this research on management of classroom practices based on modules and self-learning package on Behaviour Strategies will be fruitful. It also aids in the development of appropriate behaviour strategies for both teachers and students. It can improve students' learning and support positive classroom behaviour when implemented systematically in real classroom settings. As a result, teachers who received in-service teacher training based on the modules and self-learning package were able to significantly improve their awareness and classroom practices of Behaviour Management Strategies, as well as their students' on-task behaviour per class period. In this regard, the investigator would be well compensated if the study's findings were used by teachers, educators, and policymakers to improve current classroom management practices and to conduct more extensive research in this important but interesting and effective area.

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